

DESIGN DATA STANDARDIZATION BENEFITS

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ABSTRACT

Composite material applications have grown steadily over the past 20 years. However, with military applications rapidly diminishing, future growth depends on market diversification and technology transfer -- *both of which are dependent on industry standardization of the materials and design databases*. Industrial markets have been slow to develop because of a lack of standard engineering design data on composite materials, which increases program development time and cost to produce program-specific processes and materials design allowables. Standardization benefits include reduced qualification and raw material cost. If full standardization of the composite materials database can be achieved, the composites industry has a potential for being a \$20-billion a year business employing 250,000 people in the U.S. by 2000.

Keywords: Composites, Composite Materials, Standards, Standardization, Design Database

1.0 INTRODUCTION

"Advanced Composites" are generally synonymous with "high-performance composite materials," and refer to organic [resin] matrix materials reinforced with continuous fibers. The fibers [graphite, aramid or glass] provide high specific strength and stiffness, while the resin provides a structural bond to hold the fibers in position. Graphite fibers are often referred to as carbon fibers, and in this context may be used interchangeably. Examples of advanced composite materials include resin pre-impregnated tapes and fabrics (prepregs), sheet molding compounds, short and long fiber preforms, and reinforced film adhesives. As the materials and applications have matured, the range of materials has broadened to include advanced textile and other fiber preforms, as well as various forms of mat and chopped fiber used in sporting goods and automotive applications. The physical, chemical and structural property requirements of the materials are normally defined in a Material Specification used for procurement and receiving inspection, as well as defining requirements for testing. Each end-user of the material normally produces their own unique specification for each different composite material. In many instances a supplier sells the same material to widely different specifications, even though all materials are made on the same process line. Material specifications are produced by industry, government and commercial organizations within the U.S. The Society of Automotive Engineers [SAE], under its Aerospace Materials Specification [AMS] committee, has been responsible for developing, writing, publishing and controlling material specifications for industry use, but AMS specifications have not found wide-spread industry use.

Advanced composite materials are uniquely different from metallic materials employed in aerospace and general industry applications in that the structural properties of the material are a function of the design and are created in-situ during fabrication of the part in a tool. Complex part geometries produce locally varying fiber orientations in cured or consolidated parts, and therefore control of the manufacturing process is much more important than for metals. In addition, there are many different processes that have evolved over the past 25 years, such as autoclave cure, press forming, filament winding, pultrusion, various non-autoclave cure techniques, resin transfer molding, etc. Each process has unique processing considerations, which are normally defined in a process specification that describes and controls the process parameters, and are usually developed and validated by the user. The process specification must be explicitly followed to produce quality parts. There are no commercial process specifications in general use in the U.S. today, even though SAE has the capability for producing consensus process specifications (which SAE does for metals).

Like metallic materials, coupon and element tests are conducted to determine physical, chemical and structural properties of the material for design purposes. However, unlike homogeneous metallic materials, composite material properties are dependent upon the orientation of the laminate layup. Over the years, test methods have been developed for laminate properties, based on coupon and element test specimens, to provide material design data. Within the U.S., the American Society for Testing and Materials [ASTM], under its D-30 committee, has been the focal point for development, coordination of consensus, publishing and controlling the test methods that are in common use today. However, in many instances, there are different and conflicting test methods that have been developed for the same property, which creates problems when attempting to compare data from different sources.

Materials design data for composite materials are currently developed by each end user, based on their material and process specifications, and using company and/or ASTM testing methods and procedures. The data are analyzed using statistical methods to obtain "design allowable" properties that can be used for structural design. These *point design allowables* are normally proprietary and program-dependent, and cannot be readily transferred to other users due to differences in materials and process specifications, test methods, and analysis methods.

Over the last 20 years, the strong U.S. defense industry has provided the incentive for suppliers to improve the quality and performance of composite materials, develop new products, and increase domestic capacity of both precursor materials and finished product. Most of the major structural applications for the materials have been developed by the aerospace/defense industry for military aircraft and spacecraft applications to meet weight and performance requirements. Advanced composite materials have been identified as a critical materials technology in both defense and commercial business sectors. An analysis of data published by the Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association [SACMA] indicates that the value of advanced composite materials shipped in the Western world in 1990 was approximately \$1.38 billion. About 55% of the world market was in North America, 19% in Europe, 28% in the Pacific Rim Countries, and approximately 1% in the rest of the world. These figures do not include Soviet block production, for which reliable statistics are lacking. In 1990, projections showed that by the year 2000 the advanced composites industry would have the potential of being a \$20 billion/year business employing over 250,000 people in the U.S.

The growth experienced over the twenty years between 1969 and 1989 attracted many large international companies into the composite materials industry in the United States, Europe and Japan. These supplier companies made large investments in materials advancements and facilities over the past five years, with many of the facilities investments made at the urging of the federal government to develop domestic sources of carbon fiber. This investment in facilities increased by

Figure 1 U.S. Carbon Fiber Market Has Shown Dramatic Decrease In Projected Volume Since 1990

45% from 1989 to 1992, but is now operating at less than 50% capacity.¹ During this same time period, the forecasted composite materials usage for new military aircraft decreased by 93%, which reduced the total carbon fiber usage by approximately 50%, as indicated in Figure 1.

As the defense markets for advanced composites have continued to decline, the need for development of new markets for composite materials becomes even more critical. The survival of the composite supplier industry will rely heavily on market diversification. Composite materials offer weight and performance improvements for applications such as deep off-shore oil drilling, civil engineering/construction, chemical processing, machine tools, robotics, electric cars, medical devices, power transmission and mass transportation/high speed rail, but these high volume industrial markets are reluctant to fully embrace composite materials technology. One of the major reasons given is the lack of a standard design database for these high performance reinforced plastic materials.

2.0 STANDARDIZATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

The decrease in the defense business base and the slow growth in commercial composite applications have resulted in increased requirements for cost cutting measures to keep program costs within affordable budgets. Standardization of advanced composite materials can provide significant cost reduction potential for future military and commercial aircraft programs. Standardization must cover more than just test methods however. Standards for material and process specifications, as well as for design and quality criteria, must be achieved before design allowable data can be standardized and shared between programs effectively.

In the world of metallic structures, it is relatively easy for engineers to obtain engineering data derived from standard industry test methods and processing parameters. However, such public

information does not exist for composite materials, which severely limits use of these materials outside of the aerospace and defense markets. Increases in applications for non-aerospace products will not occur rapidly without ready and easy access to design data and analysis methods that will enable composite structures and components to be designed as easily as their metal counterparts. Non-standard materials specifications, testing and qualification standards have been identified as a major roadblock to expansion of the advanced structural materials business.² The development of a certifiable materials database and management system is critical to market diversification into industrial, commercial and civil structure applications.

Most of the composite design data generated in the aircraft industry is proprietary or non-standard, with each company relying on their own test methods to develop data for design purposes that match their individual analysis methods. Even when the data are developed under contract to the government on military aircraft programs, there is little attempt to develop standardized databases that would be usable for other programs. These shortfalls in specifications, test methods and transportable design data have been recognized for many years. However, until recently, there was not sufficient pressure on the industry or government to give up the perceived *proprietary competitive edge* that was attributed to company databases. As the defense business and the industrial base shrinks, this perceived competitive edge has steadily diminished.

3.0 BENEFITS OF STANDARDIZATION

Standardization of advanced materials databases and its related database management systems will serve to expand the market for advanced composite materials within and beyond aerospace applications to become a \$20-Billion a year business employing 250,000 people in the U.S. by the end of the century. Efforts to increase the demand and usage of advanced composites in other markets are being severely hampered by the lack of a readily accessible and reliable engineering data base on the materials. This is particularly true for those commercial markets which have been identified as having the greatest potential to use composite materials advantageously (such as mass transport and high speed rail). The lack of a structural materials database restricts the use of advanced composites on a broader scope by small business and non-aerospace commercial industries. Industry standardization would clearly go a long way to removing such restrictions.

3.1 Standardization Can Reduce Costs Of Material Qualification

The costs associated with qualification of composite materials can be excessive in comparison with overall program costs for relatively small projects due to a lack of standard design criteria approved by the Federal Aviation Administration [FAA] and the Defense Department. The lack of approved standards can result in overweight products because of concurrent design and data development programs. Each prospective user of composites must first characterize several materials before choosing the most appropriate material for their application. A manufacturer cannot always rely on a material supplier's data sheet information since the data may be based on conditions and test techniques that are not always relevant to the user. The time and effort spent on materials characterization could be better spent developing lower-cost manufacturing processes and improved product quality -- both would result in improved industry competitiveness. Lower cost is especially important if advanced composites are to achieve broader penetration of commercial markets. Standardization will also reduce the time required to introduce new products to the marketplace which not only improves a company's ability to compete, but also reduces product overhead costs.

Standardization will allow materials to be specified by industry-approved standard specifications, processing data, and property tables. Consequently, it would be a much easier task to decide on the optimal material to use for a particular application. Industrial markets are familiar with metallic

materials, which are fully characterized in the form of standard engineering design data that are readily available in certified form.³ The lack of similar supporting data on composite materials is a major complication in the lengthy process of changing from metal structures to those based on reinforced plastics. Inevitably, this additional complication lengthens the design cycle and it is often cited as one of the major reasons why industrial markets have been slow to accept these new materials.

To develop an estimate of the potential benefits that are possible by developing standards for composites, several U.S. aerospace companies and material suppliers contributed data and information on typical production programs. The example case discussed herein covers only the engineering analysis and development testing portion of a typical aircraft development program. It was assumed that a new material system was required to meet weight and performance estimates, which means that a new set of materials and design allowables data would have to be developed specifically for the new aircraft.

The total engineering effort projected for a typical advanced aircraft program can be segregated into four tasks to derive realistic cost estimates. These four tasks consist of: 1) Materials design allowables development, 2) Structural analysis methods development, 3) Element and component testing, and 3) Stress analysis. The results of these cost estimates, presented in Figure 2, represent typical values based on a survey of several recent design programs. An overall reduction of 20% in the four specified engineering activities is projected based on the above rationale. Much larger savings can be realized by considering the remaining design development activities, which will be discussed subsequently. The percentage of each task savings, before and after standardization, is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Estimated Cost Reduction For A Typical Airframe Design Project

Task	Task Effort	Task Savings	Rational
Allowables Development	%	%	
* Definition	5	50	Approved methods in place
* Fabrication & Test	85	25	Standard fixtures/procedures
* Data Reduction	10	50	Approved methods in place
Structural Analysis Development			
* Development	40	80	Approved methods in place
* Verification	60	80	Strong experience base
Element/Component Testing			
* Point Verification	70	30	Approved methods in place
* Structural Verification	30	30	Strong experience base
Stress Analysis			Approved methods in place
* Initial Analysis	100	10	Elimination of confusion
Total Cost Savings for Above Tasks -- Approximately 20%			

Figure 3. Estimated Effects of Standardization On A Typical Aircraft Design Project

3.3 Design Data Development Increases Design Span

The reduction in program costs also translates to reduced development spans, as indicated in Figure 4. Current program design spans include additional schedule time for development of design allowable data and for development of material and process specifications. Verification and optimization of the process cycle can also take up valuable program schedule, or alternatively, the material is used without optimizing the cure process, which usually creates problems with quality later in the production program. The concurrence of material design allowable data development and detail design will invariably result in overweight components if the initial projected design data are too conservative. These components will not usually be redesigned because the addition expense and time usually will not offset the weight benefits. However, unconservative projected design data can result in components that do not meet the design strength and/or life requirements, which results in additional expense to reanalyze and redesign to the revised design properties, and then to retool, fabricate and conduct new tests if the component is critical to flight safety.

3.4 Shorter Product Design Span Possible

If standardized material and process specifications and design allowables were available at the beginning of the design phase, the schedule span for development of material design allowable data can be completely eliminated. While limited testing must be conducted in-house to qualify the material and validate the material design allowables for a specific design concept, the total schedule span can be greatly diminished and the quality of the product enhanced. This produces significant savings in addition to the 20% discussed in the preceding paragraphs for the four design functions.

3.5 Reduced Material Costs And Expanded Markets Possible

Lack of standardization, from a material suppliers' perspective, continues to be a major barrier to market diversification and profitability. Reductions in overall manufacturing costs are essential to

Figure 4. Standard Design Allowables Can Shorten Design Span

promote market development as well as reduce the capital investments and long times needed to bring new products to market. The use of standardized process specifications, statistical control techniques, test methods, product certification practices and qualification database methodologies will significantly reduce supplier and user costs. Material suppliers have estimated that standardization could result in a 10-20% reduction in material costs to the user. The cost reduction is dependent upon the complexity of the process and product testing requirements. There are examples of materials on the market today where commercial versions of the same fiber/prepreg are sold at prices 20-25% lower than the same material sold to a unique customer specification. The major contributor to this cost differential is the cost of testing and certification to the unique customer requirements. As an example, Hercules has sold AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepreg tape to 11 different material specifications, and IM6/3501-6 carbon/epoxy prepreg fabric to 12 different material specifications over the past several years. This greatly increases the cost of the material when compared to qualification to a single material specification and development of a single shared properties database.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

While the preceding examples demonstrate relative savings, they do not provide an indication of the total value of cost savings that could be expected from standardization. This type of data is difficult to obtain because of the proprietary nature of most cost data. However, several industry specialists were consulted and agreed that a savings of \$2-3 million per major airframe design program would be conservative. These savings would quickly pay back the cost of standardization. The cost to develop databases on materials used for commercial applications would be significantly lower due

to fewer and reduced requirements.

While the number of airframe design programs are rapidly decreasing,⁴ these savings are still important. The data from the Reference 4 article on new airframe starts was used to estimate that \$30 - 50 million could have been saved over the past 20 years if standardized data had been available for all airframe designs that used composite materials. This would have easily offset the cost of any standardization program, resulting in a net savings to industry and government while also expanding the applications for composite materials.

4.1 Prospects For Technology Transfer Will Be Improved

Technology transfer is becoming an important issue in today's highly competitive world. A number of U.S. industrial consortia have a specific interest in advanced structural composite materials. They have recognized the need to address the lack of progress in transferring technology from aerospace and defense industries or from government and university research labs to the manufacturing floor. Organizations such as the Institute for Manufacturing and Automation Research [IMAR], the Composites Automation Consortium [CAC], the National Center for Manufacturing Sciences [NCMS], the Automotive Composites Consortium, Inc. [ACC], and Composite Materials Characterization, Inc. [CMC], are all concerned with standardization as it relates to enhancing the technology transfer process while providing reduced costs. The view is shared that it will be very difficult to transfer technology from the aerospace sector without first establishing engineering data in a form that is easily understood and absorbed by commercial industries.

Increased market diversification, reduced material qualification costs and more rapid technology transfer are all possible with industry standardization. The end result will be an advanced composites industry that is stronger, more financially viable and more competitive in global markets. There is also an opportunity for the USA and other countries to cooperate in the development of international standards through interaction with international standards organizations.

5.0 REFERENCES

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